

similar diphenyl¹⁰ derivative shown to have a *cis*-structure. In the present case also, the higher values of dipole moment (5.8μ) as well as the spectral studies of the diphenyl lead bis-Schiff base derivatives indicate that the two phenyl groups are present at the *cis*-position, whereas the dialkyl metal bis-Schiff base derivatives (Table 1) have a *trans*-structure as indicated below.

where, $M = \text{Si, Ge, Sn or Pb}$; $R = \text{Me, Et or Bu}$.

As all the above derivatives have the same symmetry (octahedral structure)⁹⁻¹¹ almost similar values of dipole moments are expected. However, the role of the metal ion cannot be completely ruled out and slight variations in the dipole moments can be explained on the basis of the differences in the electronegativities of the respective elements and the possible role of $p\pi-d\pi$ bonding in the chelates.

The dipole moments of the molecular complexes of iodine with Me_2SiL_2 , Bu_2GeL_2 , Bu_2SnL_2 , Et_2PbL_2 , as well as the ligand (L) were calculated by the same procedure and the data are enlisted in Table 1. An increase in the dipole moment values has been noted on complexation with iodine and on this basis it can be concluded that the resulting molecular complexes with iodine are of charge-transfer type.

TABLE 1—DIPOLE MOMENT VALUES (μ) OF SCHIFF BASE COMPLEXES AND THE CORRESPONDING MOLECULAR COMPLEXES WITH IODINE

Sl. no.	R	M	μ values (Debye)	
			R_2ML_2	$R_2ML_2 \cdot I_2$
1.	Me	Si	0.745	1.075
2.	Bu	Ge	0.822	1.142
3.	Bu	Sn	0.885	1.159
4.	Et	Pb	0.924	1.174

In the infrared spectra the ν_{C-N} vibrations ($\sim 1620 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the R_2ML_2) remain unaltered in the corresponding molecular complexes of iodine ($R_2ML_2 \cdot I_2$), showing thereby the non-involvement of azomethine nitrogen; the only probability for the formation of these complexes is the donation of electron density through the ring of the acetylacetonate to the iodine molecule and thus providing an additional support to the pseudo-aromatic character of these chelate rings.

The electronic spectra of ligands exhibit three bands around 250, 315 and 400 nm. The bands around 250 and 315 nm are possibly due to $\pi-\pi^*$

transitions of benzenoid ring in conjugation with double band of azomethine group¹², and the band around 400 nm may be due to the $n-\pi^*$ transition¹³ of bonding electrons present on the nitrogen of the azomethine group. In the corresponding aluminium complexes, there is no shift in the position of the first two bands. The ligand band around 400 nm shows bathochromic shifts of 20 nm in the complexes and this may be due to the coordination of nitrogens of azomethine groups to the central aluminium atom. However, in the case of molecular complexes of iodine there is no shift in the position of this band, which further confirms the above observations of ir spectra that in the molecular complexes of iodine, the azomethine nitrogens do not take part in coordination.

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Aquo-bis(diethyldithiocarbamate)nitrosyl Chromium(I)

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AFTER the isolation of potassium salt of nitrosyl-pentacyanochromate(I)¹, several other cationic complexes of hexacoordinated chromium(I)^{2,3} have been reported. However, only a few neutral complexes of nitrosyl Cr^I have been characterised^{4,5}. We report the isolation and characterisation of a new hexacoordinated complex of monovalent chromium containing diethyldithiocarbamate as ligand.

Experimental

Preparation of complex: Potassiumpentacyanonitrosylchromate(I) hydrate (1.0 g) was dissolved in water (30 ml) and to it an aqueous solution of sodiumdiethyldithiocarbamate (1.0 g) was added. Acetic acid (1 : 1, 10 ml) was then slowly added with constant stirring and the issuing gas chased by a current of carbon dioxide, whereby a reddish brown precipitate appeared which was filtered and washed several times with water. The precipitate was extracted with acetone and the reddish brown compound was reprecipitated by adding petroleum ether and dried (35%), (Found: Cr, 13.2; C, 30.1; N, 10.5; H, 5.56; mol. wt. 410. $\text{CrNO}(\text{DTC})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ requires Cr, 13.1; C, 30.3; N, 10.6; H, 5.5%; mol. wt. 396).

Analysis: Chromium was determined as Cr_2O_3 after decomposing the complex by heating with alkali followed by dissolution in nitric acid and precipitating by NH_4OH . Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were determined microanalytically.

Physical methods: Conductance was measured in analytical grade methanol using a dip type cell on a Philips conductivity bridge. Molecular weight of the compound was determined by Rast's method using camphor as solvent. Magnetic susceptibility was measured on powdered sample using Gouy balance. The apparatus was calibrated using cobalt mercury thiocyanate. The parallel and perpendicular components of the 'g' value were obtained on powdered sample using potassium bromide as diluent. This measurement was done using a Varian-4502 spectrometer and DPPH was used as internal standard. Infrared spectrum was recorded in KBr disc using a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The complex is soluble in alcohol, acetone and acetonitrile to impart orange colour and insoluble in petroleum ether. In methanol, the complex is found to be non-electrolytic in nature ($\Lambda_M = 17.3 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$). The μ_{eff} value of 1.73 B.M. at 303K for the complex and 'g' value of 1.990 of powdered compound ($g_{\text{I}} = 1.997$ and $g_{\text{II}} = 1.982$ for esr spectrum of the compound diluted with KBr), is consistent with a low-spin d^5 configuration of Cr^{I} ^{6,7}. Its ir spectrum shows a very strong band⁸ at 1705 cm^{-1} (NO^+). The broad bands at 3540 and 3480 cm^{-1} and the shoulder at 1620 cm^{-1} are due to ν_{OH} and $\delta_{\text{H-O-H}}$, respectively. The bands at 620 and 575 cm^{-1} can be assigned to $\nu_{\text{Cr-N}}$ and $\delta_{\text{Cr-N-O}}$, respectively as reported by Miki⁹ and the author⁵. The band at 1490 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ and single band at 995 cm^{-1} for $\nu_{\text{O-S}}$ are indicative of the bidentate coordination of dithiocarbamate ligand¹⁰. On the basis of above data, an octahedral structure may be proposed for the complex.

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Kinetics of Chromic Acid Oxidation of Some Hydroxy Acids

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THE chromic acid oxidation of some hydroxy acids have been studied earlier¹⁻³. The kinetics of chromic acid oxidation of hydroxy acid having a substituent on the α -carbon have been reported⁴⁻⁷. But the reports do not reveal the process of oxidation of hydroxy acids by chromium(VI). This paper reports the results of the process of oxidation of hydroxy acids by chromium(VI).

Experimental

The hydroxy acids were of A.R. grade and the other chemicals including $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ were of G.R. (E. Merck) grade. 60% HClO_4 (E. Merck) was used as the source of hydrogen ion. The solvents were purified by standard procedures.

Kinetic measurements: The rate of consumption of Cr^{VI} was followed spectrophotometrically by measuring the optical density on a Backman DU spectrophotometer at different intervals. In some cases the consumption of Cr^{VI} was determined iodometrically^{2,8-10}. Some experiments, under identical conditions, were conducted both iodometrically and